

Speculative Realism in Speculative Fiction

Abstract: At the beginning of the 21st century, with the rise of "speculative realism" in philosophy, speculative fiction in literature has grown increasingly fast. Speculative realism breaks through the limitations of traditional realism, constructing a multidimensional understanding of reality. As a result, speculative realism merges the deep connection between literary realism and philosophical realism, illuminating a new contemporary perspective on reality in speculative literature. Simultaneously, from the standpoint of cognitive science, it introduces concepts of "cognitive truth" and "the reality of thought" as frameworks for understanding reality. By analyzing the typical themes and narrative strategies of speculative fiction, this paper proposes speculative realism criticism in literature. It not only reconstructs the ways literature expresses reality but also fosters interdisciplinary dialogue among literary theory, philosophy, and cognitive science. This expands the theoretical boundaries of realism and deepens our understanding of literature, society, and the existential questions of humanity.

Key words: speculative realism; realism; speculative fiction; literary criticism;
The Handmaid's Tale

Introduction

Realism, as a literary tradition, has been a dominant mode of Western novelistic writing since the 18th century. It emphasizes a faithful representation of objective reality and seeks to reveal the truth of social life through detailed description and causal logic. However, the core question of realism—what constitutes the “real”—has always been a central point of debate in literary theory. Since the rise of modern philosophy, realism as an epistemological and ontological stance has profoundly influenced the construction of literary realism. In particular, the emergence of 19th-century realistic fiction is closely linked to the traditions of empiricism and

realism stemming from thinkers like Descartes and Locke. During this period, literature gradually shifted from the depiction of collective experiences to the representation of individual experience, turning realistic literature into a vehicle for expressing personal subjectivity. In the 20th century, modernist and postmodernist literature challenged the objectivity of realism, highlighting the constructed nature of texts and the indeterminacy of language. At the same time, the philosophical domain underwent the “linguistic turn,” as realism was increasingly supplanted by constructivism, phenomenology, and post-structuralism. However, in the early 21st century, emerging philosophical movements such as Speculative Realism began to reexamine the limitations of anthropocentrism and reassert the independence of reality. This shift has had a direct impact on literature, giving rise to a new transgeneric mode—speculative fiction. As Marek Oziwicz summarized in *Oxford Research Encyclopedias, Literature* that speculative fiction as “non-mimetic genres may be potentially more adequate than the so-called realistic literature to address contemporary global challenges and reflect the diverse perspectives, traditions, and experiences of the multicultural world”(Oziwicz,2017:9).

Based on the background above, this paper proposes speculative realism writing in literature, tracing the philosophical origins of realism and philosophical realism before analyzing the core theoretical framework of speculative realism. It examines the characteristic themes of speculative realistic literature—such as visions of future societies, gender and racial issues—revealing how speculative narratives explore the boundaries of reality. Finally, the study outlines a framework of speculative realism criticism in literature, demonstrating how it proposes a new realistic approach in the post-postmodern era, thereby redefining literature's modes of representing reality.◦

1.Realism

Literary realism and philosophical realism belong to the domains of literature and philosophy, respectively. Although they differ in their fields and modes of expression, both are concerned with “reality,” emphasizing the representation or

cognition of external reality and seeking to address core questions such as “What is reality?” and “How do we understand it?” Their philosophical roots lie in the Western philosophical tradition, which has driven profound insights into the nature of reality across different historical periods.

In literature, M.H. Abrams provides a dual definition of "realism" in *A Glossary of Literary Terms*, distinguishing between its broad and narrow senses. In the narrow sense, it refers to the 19th-century novelistic movement... In the broad sense, it encompasses literary works from various historical periods that center on "representing human life and experience". Moreover, from the reader's perspective, he interprets the purpose of "realistic fiction is written to give the effect that it represents life and the social world as it seems to the common reader, evoking the sense that hat its characters might in fact exist, and that such things might well happen". David Mikics defines realism in *A New Handbook of Literary Terms* that “is to tell the truth, brushing away fantasies and wishful, idealized versions of the world...and the acceptance of the hard facts of life”.

In the field of philosophy, “the basic idea of realism is that the kinds of thing which exist, and what they are like, are independent of us and the way in which we find out about them”, according to *Routledge Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. (Craig, 1998 : 7236) This is similar to Nicholas Bunnin's explanation of traditional realism:“the central idea of realism is that things of a certain problematic sort exist independent of our minds,whether or not we know or believe them to exist” in *The Blackwell Dictionary of Western Philosophy*.Thus, realism asserts that the real or reality exists independently of human consciousness and perception; the existence and properties of objective things do not depend on human cognitive activity. In this sense, realism deals with the epistemological category of “reality,” and the aim of our inquiry is to understand which objects of knowledge in the world truly exist, in what way they exist, and how we humans can come to discover them.

The philosophical roots of literary realism and realism as a philosophical doctrine are deeply embedded in the Western philosophical tradition, enabling them to express profound insights into truth in varying forms across different historical

periods. The rise of literary realism was not merely an innovation in narrative aesthetics but was fundamentally grounded in the Western philosophical tradition's core assumptions about "reality" and "truth." Its central premise lies in the belief that the real world is knowable and representable—that language and narrative can approximate, if not fully convey, the objective structures of the external world. This conviction directly inherits the foundational stance of philosophical realism, which posits the existence of an objective reality independent of human perception and symbolic systems. While imperfect, knowledge and language can, to some degree, approach or even reveal this reality.

Starting from Aristotle's theory of mimesis, literature has been endowed with an epistemological function—to represent nature, human action, and the essence of humanity. This imitation is not a mere act of copying, but a cognitive practice that elevates individual experience into universal form. This line of thought was further developed in the empiricist and Enlightenment philosophies of the 18th and 19th centuries, particularly in the works of philosophers such as Locke and Hume who emphasized perception, induction, and empirical methods. These theories not only laid the foundation for scientific knowledge but also permeated literary realism's focus on details, social causality, historical context, and individual psychology.

However, philosophical reflections from the late 19th to the 20th century gradually exposed the internal tensions of realism's ontology. Kant, through his distinction between the “thing-in-itself” and the “phenomenal world,” argued that human cognition is always constrained by a priori categories and perceptual structures, thereby undermining the belief that reality can be directly accessed. Subsequently, phenomenology, philosophy of language, structuralism, and post-structuralism further deconstructed the presumed transparency of representation, asserting that language, consciousness, and cultural structures are themselves the conditions through which “reality” is constructed. Against this backdrop, literary realism came to be seen not as a neutral reflection of the world, but as an ideological construct—its notion of the “real” merely a naturalized expression of a particular worldview shaped by its historical context.

Nevertheless, the quest for reality has never ceased in either literature or philosophy. Since the 21st century, speculative realism—as a philosophical turn toward new realism—has once again challenged the hegemony of linguistic centrism and correlationism, advocating for a renewed contemplation of "being itself" beyond anthropocentric constraints. This intellectual movement has opened possibilities for reconfiguring literary realism: not through a return to the reductionist paradigms of classical realism, but by forging a speculative path that transcends the confines of mundane empirical depiction and instead navigates the terrain of subjective cognition. It is within this theoretical framework that this study proposes speculative realism as a literary mode, whose essence lies in employing literary practice to persistently explore the multidimensional interplay between subjective cognition, textual mechanics, and existence.

2. Philosophical Foundation

The term "speculation" originates from the Latin *speculum*, meaning "mirror, reflection, and reflective consciousness". Its root, *spek-*, derives from the Proto-Indo-European language, carrying the sense of "to observe." Thus, the original meaning of "speculation" is "reflective observation". The etymology of "speculation" belongs to the realms of philosophy and theology, where it describes the act of pondering and reflectively observing the unknown. In *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of the Possible*, Arran Gare outlines several defining characteristics of speculation from a philosophical perspective: first, it questions the certainty of things. "Speculation potentially brings everything into question, beginning with appearances and beliefs, methods of inquiry and knowledge of methods for acquiring and ascertaining claims to knowledge"(1537). Second, it seeks new worldviews and alternatives. Speculation emphasizes interrogation and exploration without confinement to specific domains, proposing fresh ways of thinking and directions for action. Third, speculation represents humanity's experiential cognitive development, highlighting the dynamic interplay between experience, concepts, and intellectual growth. By continually

questioning established concepts and generating new ones to explain emerging experiences, this iterative process of conceptual renewal constitutes speculation itself. As a philosophical method, speculation applies equally to science, art, and history because thought is "inherently synthetic"(ibid.) in nature.

Speculative realism serves as the philosophical foundation for literary speculative realism. In the early 21st century, as philosophers began critiquing post-Kantian "correlationism", the speculative realism movement emerged. Originating from a 2007 London symposium, this philosophical school was pioneered by thinkers including Quentin Meillassoux, Graham Harman, Ray Brassier, and Iain Hamilton Grant, who developed four distinct branches. Among these, Harman's "Object-Oriented Ontology" (OOO) gained particular prominence, sparking widespread scholarly interest. The core proposition of speculative realism maintains that reality possesses objectivity, yet human rationality cannot fully apprehend it—only through imagination can we approach this objectivity. While inheriting traditional realism's fundamental premise of reality's independence, speculative realism simultaneously critiques and transcends classical realistic thought. It seeks to investigate broader ontological questions, liberating itself from modern philosophy's anthropocentric tendencies to examine reality's autonomous existence and the being of non-human entities.

Speculative realism shares an intrinsic and profound connection with speculative fiction. As Graham Harman, one of the founding philosophers of speculative realism, states in the editorial preface in *Speculative Realism and Science Fiction*:

From the moment that Speculative Realism was born in 2007, its connections with science fiction were both obvious and openly declared. Both currents hope to draw us away from academic fixation on the infinite subtleties of human cognition, and into a larger speculative cosmos. Admittedly, there seem to be two distinct missions at work here: science fiction often portrays a universe that is an imaginative fabrication of the author; Speculative Realism, as a type of philosophy, is duty-bound to speak about the world as it is. Yet the two traditions soon draw closer again when we realise that Speculative Realism, in all its

variations, tends to uphold a reality that is significantly more bizarre than that accepted by everyday common sense. (vii)

Speculative realism and science fiction share profound conceptual resonances at their core, as both challenge humanity's monopolistic explanation of reality. Each pushes against the boundaries of "commonsense reality", elevating the "unthinkable" into serious intellectual inquiry: science fiction through narrative experimentation, philosophy through logical argumentation—yet both ultimately converge on the revelation that reality may be far stranger than we imagine. Thus, the connection between speculative realism and speculative fiction is objectively verifiable, with their intersection lying in their shared pursuit of answering "what is reality".

3. Speculative Realism and literary studies

Academic research applying speculative realism to literary analysis has primarily developed along four key dimensions. Firstly, when speculative realism first entered the field of literary studies, scholars primarily focused on how it constructs a non-human philosophical perspective and narrative aesthetics through Gothic, grotesque, and science fiction literature. In his 2012 book *Weird Realism: Lovecraft and Philosophy*, Graham Harman introduced the ideas of speculative realism into the analysis of H. P. Lovecraft's work from the perspective of OOO (Harman, 2012). He argues that Lovecraft's weird aesthetics reveal a reality that transcends human perception, positioning speculative realism as a crucial tool for understanding the presence of the "non-human" in literature. *Speculative Realism and Science Fiction* is a scholarly monograph by Brian Willems that offers an in-depth exploration of the relationship between speculative realism and science fiction literature. The book analyzes how science fiction, through its unique narrative strategies, embodies the core concepts of speculative realism—particularly the "Zug Effect," which refers to the depiction of "dark objects" in science fiction: entities that cannot be fully understood or explained (Willems, 2017). Through close readings of science fiction texts, the book demonstrates how the genre functions as a philosophical tool, enabling

us to reflect on realities beyond the human and on the complex relationships between the human and the non-human.

Secondly, speculative realism offers ethnic literature and historical narratives a transformative pathway beyond traditional realism, particularly through "historical fantasy" as a means to reconfigure expressions of identity and justice. In his essay "Historical Fantasy, Speculative Realism, and Postrace Aesthetics," Ramón Saldivar identifies an emerging trend in 21st-century U.S. ethnic fiction that hybridizes "historical fantasy" with speculative realism (Saldivar, 2011). His analysis demonstrates how ethnic novels (e.g., works by Plascencia and Díaz) employ fantastical elements and non-linear narration to interrogate race and justice within postracial discourses. Crucially, Saldivar highlights speculative realism's capacity to dismantle conventional realistic frameworks while reimagining the construction of history and identity.

Thirdly, as a form of speculative aesthetics, speculative realism redefines the aesthetic experience of literature by viewing fantastic literature as a medium for philosophical perception. A representative work of this perspective is *The Universe of Things: On Speculative Realism*, in which Steven Shaviro advocates for understanding speculative realism as a "speculative aesthetics," emphasizing its role in the aesthetic experience of literature and art rather than solely as a philosophical stance. He argues that the value of fantastic literature lies in its ability to stimulate "speculative perception," proposing that aesthetic experience itself constitutes a mode of philosophical insight (Shaviro, 2014).

Fourthly, research on the relationship between speculative realism and romanticism or realism reveals their shared philosophical concerns regarding the nature of reality and the relationship between nature and humanity. Evan Gottlieb was among the first to explore the connection between British Romantic poetry and speculative realism in his scholarly monograph *Romantic Realities: Speculative Realism and British Romanticism*. Through an interdisciplinary approach, this book analyzes how romantic poets resonate with the philosophical themes of speculative realism—particularly in their reflections on the essence of reality, the condition of the

natural world, and the relationship between humanity and the world (Gottlieb, 2016). By drawing comparisons and connections between romantic poets and speculative realism philosophers, Gottlieb highlights the shared themes and methodologies they employ to interrogate reality, nature, and human subjectivity. Following this, Chris Washington and Anne C. McCarthy edited the volume *Romanticism and Speculative Realism*, which further investigates the links between the two, proposing that romanticism offers important intellectual resources for speculative realism. This collection brings together a range of scholarly perspectives on the deep affinities between romantic literature and speculative realism. In their introduction, Washington and McCarthy argue that the connection between romanticism and speculative realism is far from incidental; rather, the romantic tradition's profound insights into human subjectivity and the natural world have laid crucial groundwork for speculative realistic thought. Stefano Ercolino's *Realism and Dialectic: The Speculative Turn and the History of the Nineteenth-Century European Novel* deserves special attention. This article centers on the evolution of realism in 19th-century European fiction, particularly its dialectical relationship between narrative form, setting, and speculative impulses (Ercolino, 2020). Through an in-depth analysis of Fredric Jameson's concept of "the unity of opposites" in realism, Ercolino reveals the dialectical tension within realistic novels between narrative and setting. He introduces the concept of the "speculative impulse" to explore how it influenced the development of realism. The article also examines the "speculative turn" in the latter half of the 19th century and its profound impact on the narrative structure of realism fiction.

The application of speculative realism in literary studies has evolved through several phases—from analyses of Gothic fiction to science fiction, ecocriticism, and ultimately realistic fiction. Particularly in examining themes such as non-human perspectives, technological objects, and ecological horror, it has emerged as a powerful theoretical framework. Future research could further integrate philosophy and literary criticism to explore the multidimensional relationships between text and reality. However, it is crucial to recognize that philosophical concepts cannot be directly equated with literary ones. The literary exploration of speculation and reality

possesses its own distinct characteristics. While speculative realism provides literary studies with a set of theoretical tools, its translation into literary research demands fresh insights into literary language, narrative forms, and aesthetic qualities. This constitutes the core concern of the present study.

Speculative realism constitutes a literary theoretical exploration grounded in philosophical speculative realism. It refers to a cognitive and conceptual dimension of truth that differs fundamentally from traditional realism's imitation and representation of sensory experience. Manifested through the highly abstract, generalized, and intellectualized cognitive authenticity of three narrative agents—the author, narrator, and characters—this approach rejects faithful replication of the empirical world. Instead, it emphasizes profound interrogation and logical deduction of real-world contradictions and problems at the level of human cognition. From this perspective, we can comprehend those grotesque, absurd, and fantastical narrative forms in fiction that defy conventional realistic conventions—not as breaks from reality, but as cognitive mappings of reality's deeper structures. The speculative realistic text thus operates as a thought experiment testing reality's boundaries, a conceptual apparatus revealing latent contradictions, and a cognitive interface mediating between thought and world.

4. Speculative realism's conception of reality

The "conception of reality" in speculative realism of literature manifests in the following aspects:

Unlike traditional realism, speculative realism places greater emphasis on the reality of the imaginary—even if the depicted objects do not empirically exist, their representations often transcend human experiential reality. In this regard, it appears closer to romanticism. As Harman observes in *Romantic Realities: Speculative Realism and British Romanticism*: "Opposing the formerly ubiquitous modern dogma that philosophy can speak only of the human-world relation rather than the world itself, Speculative Realism defends the autonomy of the world from human access,

but in a spirit of imaginative audacity" (Gottlieb, 2016)

The reality in speculative realism is characterized by uncertainty, ambiguity, and openness. Whereas traditional realism presupposes linear and deterministic causality, speculative realism emphasizes reality's uncertainty, contingency, and non-linear causal relations. As Stéphane Vanderhaeghe states in *Dear Incomprehension—On American Speculative Fiction* that “the unfolding sentence would remain indefinitely open onto its paradigmatic axis as each new word is added; no longer oriented toward an end that would make it susceptible to yielding meaning or closure, the speculative sentence would participate instead in a regime of mutation, of transformation, generation, iteration, even perhaps simulation.” (9)

The works of speculative realism are, in essence, a form of thought experiment that typically articulates the author's pluralistic visions of possibility. Michael Kramp notes in his examination of late Victorian novels that “the speculative fiction of the late-Victorian period models immense creativity and provides prospects of volatile hopes that remain threatening—and exciting.” (Kramp, 2024: 4) Marek Oziewicz similarly expressed this view that “speculative fiction is as essential to our humanness as conditionals, past, and future tenses are for our language. They keep our dreaming alive...” (Oziewicz, 2015: 4)

5. Speculative realism's themes, linguistic and narrative features

In terms of themes, speculative realistic works explore social, political, and cultural issues in reality to construct narratives with a high degree of criticality and reflexivity. Speculative fiction centers on hypotheses or conjectures from philosophy, sociology, technology, and other fields, thereby engaging in profound examinations of the real world. Broadly speaking, the typical themes of such literary works primarily include: the construction and evolution of future societies (e.g., George Orwell's *1984*, Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World*, Margaret Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale*), ontological depictions of technological alienation (e.g., Kim Stanley Robinson's *2312*),

environmental degradation and ecological crises (e.g., Neal Stephenson's *Snow Crash*), gender and societal speculation (e.g., Ursula K. Le Guin's *The Left Hand of Darkness*), and imaginings of ethnic and cultural diversity (e.g., Nalo Hopkinson's *Brown Girl in the Ring*).

In terms of language, speculative realism detaches itself from the narrative framework of the textual world and instead constructs meaning through atemporal speculative discourse. Formally, it frequently employs modality markers, including: modal auxiliaries (must/might/may/should/will/could...), modal adverbs (probably/maybe/perhaps...), epistemic verbs and adverbs (know/think/seem...), etc. These linguistic features reflect the speculative, hypothetical, or uncertain attitudes, perspectives, and inferences of characters or narrators. Stylistically, authors often use free direct discourse—speech without quotation marks that directly conveys the perspectives of the author, narrator, or characters—to create a "figure" effect, where the quoted content is visually and thematically emphasized. For example, in *The Handmaid's Tale*, Margaret Atwood constructs the dystopian theocracy of Gilead, illustrating how religion is weaponized as a political tool to justify the oppression of women and society at large. In Chapter 14, before the ritualized "Ceremony," Offred and her family are permitted to watch state-controlled news broadcasts—a propaganda tool meticulously curated to showcase only regime-approved "victories." Observing the edited footage and the expressions of prisoners, Offred speculates whether these images are fabricated or selectively presented. This triggers her speculative reasoning:

...the news.

Such as it is: who knows **if** any of it is true? It **could** be old clips, it **could** be faked. (Atwood, 2010: 92)

They show us only victories, never defeats. Who wants bad news?

Possibly he's an actor.(Atwood, 2010: 93)

Atwood employs these standalone speculative passages to expose the manipulation of information and the erosion of truth under totalitarianism. The

protagonist's speculation directly challenges the authenticity of the news, implying that Gilead, like historical authoritarian regimes (e.g., Nazi Germany, the Soviet Union), controls public perception through fabricated or selectively curated reporting. Gilead's propaganda machine showcases only "victories" while concealing failures, crafting an illusion of invincibility. This one-sided narrative strips people of their ability to judge reality, rendering them blindly obedient. The ethical core of this speculative discourse lies in its revelation of how totalitarianism sustains power by distorting information—depriving citizens of their right to know and think critically. The skepticism toward "news" in speculative fiction is fundamentally rooted in real-world social issues, particularly Atwood's firsthand experience with authoritarian politics during her 1984 visit to East Germany. As she noted in an interview:

During our stay we also visited East Berlin, as well as Poland 'and Czechoslovakia, and I thus had several first-hand experiences of the flavour of life in a totalitarian – but supposedly utopian – regime. I wrote more of the book (*The Handmaid's Tale*) once I was back in Toronto...

(Atwood, "Margaret Atwood," 2011)

In terms of narrative strategy, when the author engages in "speculation" on a particular topic, the narrative perspective often shifts to the second person. This shift in pronoun usage manifests in two ways: 1) standalone paragraphs—typically representing the narrator's discursive commentary; 2) embedded passages—usually reflecting a character's internal monologue without formal distinction. This technique is not merely a stylistic choice but serves as the writer's deliberate demarcation between reality and the speculative realm. By adopting the second-person perspective ("you"), the reader is directly immersed into the speculative world of the character or narrator. This narrative device suggests the universality of speculative thinking: it transcends being merely an individual's cognitive process within the text and becomes a potential mental state for the reader as well. Through this approach, the writer elevates personal consciousness into a form of collective philosophical inquiry. For instance, at the beginning of Chapter 23, the protagonist Offred lies alone, imagining a future where she might escape the totalitarian regime of Gilead. Here, Atwood

employs the second-person perspective to dissolve the boundary between Offred's private hopes and the reader's own contemplative engagement, transforming individual yearning into a broader meditation on resistance and freedom.

When I get out of here, if I'm ever able to set this down, in any form, even in the form of one voice to another, it will be a reconstruction then too, at yet another remove. It's impossible to say a thing exactly the way it was, because what you say can never be exact, you always have to leave something out, there are too many parts, sides, crosscurrents, nuances; too many gestures, which could mean this or that, too many shapes which can never be fully described, too many flavours, in the air or on the tongue, half-colours, too many. But if you happen to be a man, sometime in the future, and you've made it this far, please remember: you will never be subjected to the temptation of feeling you must forgive, a man, as a woman. It's difficult to resist, believe me. But remember that forgiveness too is a power. To beg for it is a power, and to withhold or bestow it is a power, perhaps the greatest.(Atwood, 2010: 144)

As the protagonist begins with a hypothetical inference ("if") to reflect on how she might record this history after her escape, the consecutive use of two positively weighted epistemic modal expressions ("will," "it is impossible...") powerfully conveys the narrator's stance on the grand themes of history and truth. Any narrative is a form of *reconstruction*, never a complete restoration of fact. Language itself is inherently limited, incapable of capturing the full complexity of reality ("too many parts, sides, crosscurrents, nuances"). As Jacques Derrida has argued, the structure of language and its system of signs inevitably lead to the *différance* of meaning, so language cannot directly reflect reality—instead, it distorts, omits, or even reshapes it. Taking this opportunity, the author calls historical narration into question, prompting the reader to be wary of everything being told, and to recognize that the novel itself is also a *reconstruction*, not a record of “real” history. In the sentence, “*But if you*

happen to be a man, sometime in the future, and you've made it this far, please remember: you will never be subjected to the temptation of feeling you must forgive, a man," the author shifts the narrative perspective, employing the second-person pronoun "you" four times. Here, the narration no longer remains within the realm of possible-world character activity, but instead enters the narrator's speculative domain. Atwood raises a feminist question: how does forgiveness become a burden passively borne by women, while men are exempt from such moral dilemmas? In a patriarchal society, women are expected to forgive, to understand, and to endure the transgressions of men. Yet men rarely face the same "pressure to forgive"—they can escape culpability, while women are continually urged to let go. *"Forgiveness is itself a right. To ask for forgiveness is a right, and to grant or withhold forgiveness is an even greater right—perhaps the greatest."* This sentence articulates the author's speculative reflection on morality and power: forgiveness is not always a moral virtue—it is embedded within power relations. The use of the modal "perhaps," expressing uncertainty, once again reminds female readers: you have the right *not* to forgive, and this is, in itself, a form of power. As Essi Varis and colleagues assert, "speculation is inherently dialogic... it never occurs in isolation; we are always immersed in prior social interactions" (Varis et al., 2023: 112). Through the writing of a speculative world, the author reflects the asymmetries of gendered power structures in the real world—an effort to provoke readers' critical thinking, dialogue, and resonance to the fullest extent.

At the level of narrative voice, the use of an unreliable narrator draws the reader's attention to the incompleteness of the narration, thereby prompting doubt about the authenticity of what is called "reality." Yet it is precisely through this uncertainty and ambiguity that a more philosophically resonant form of *cognitive realism* emerges—one that is not concerned with the accuracy of facts, but with how individuals perceive, experience, question, and construct reality. For example, in *The Handmaid's Tale*, Offred, as an unreliable first-person narrator, shifts between clarity

and obscurity, between calm analysis and indulgent fantasy. She frequently revises or corrects herself, as in:

I made that up. It didn't happen that way. Here is what happened.(273)

...

This is the story, then.

I went back to Nick.(280)

...

I told you it was bad.

Here is how it goes.(280)

This repeated self-denial and retrospective narration marks her as a quintessential unreliable narrator. However, this is not a narrative flaw or mere stylistic device—it is a genuine reflection of the narrator's cognitive condition. Her perspective reveals the fragmentation of perception under a totalitarian regime, the unverifiability of memory, and the inaccessibility of truth.

In terms of narrative structure, speculative fiction often adopts open-ended conclusions. Rather than adhering to the linear causality of the empirical world, it gestures toward a higher-order, more abstract form of cognitive realism—one that reflects the inherent uncertainty and incompleteness of the world itself. For example, at the end of Margaret Atwood's *Oryx and Crake*, the protagonist "Snowman" (Snowman/Jimmy) discovers three surviving humans approaching. Armed and hidden in the underbrush, he faces three possible courses of action: to step forward and engage with them in an attempt to establish new social bonds; to remain hidden, continuing his solitary existence and preserving the status quo; or to attack them, eliminating a potential threat and maintaining his role as the last survivor. The novel does not disclose Snowman's decision; instead, it ends abruptly with his inner monologue—"What should he do?" This is not merely a narrative cliffhanger. Rather, it poses three philosophical questions concerning human morality, cognitive capacity, and the logic of survival. It reflects Atwood's pursuit of a deeper kind of truth

characteristic of speculative fiction—truth at the level of thought—and offers the reader a space to imagine, and perhaps hope for, the future of human existence.

Conclusion

"Speculative Realism" is a literary-theoretical inquiry grounded in the philosophical movement of speculative realism. It focuses on complex issues in the real world that cannot be grasped through direct experience, emphasizing a philosophical and speculative construction of reality on the levels of cognition, language, and thought. In contrast to traditional realism's faithful depiction of everyday experience and the sensory world, speculative realism in literature presents a kind of *cognitive reality*—a reality generated through the intellectual activity of the author, narrator, and characters. This form of reality transcends surface-level experience and rejects subject-centered perspectives, thereby expanding the representational scope of realist literature. This *imagined real* is the very foundation of speculative realism: it does not seek to imitate surface reality, but rather uses hypothesis, imagination, and the speculative capacities of language and thought to challenge the notion that "seeing is believing," and to explore the multiple dimensions and latent possibilities of what reality might be. Writers construct cognitive expressions of reality through multiple dimensions: specific themes (such as ecological crisis, technological alienation, the reconstruction of gendered power relations, and the reorganization of social systems), lexical choices, syntactic structures, rhetorical strategies, and narrative techniques. Ultimately, this multidimensional literary practice collectively forms a kind of cognitive realism that transcends traditional realism—one that remains deeply engaged with real-world issues while simultaneously expanding the boundaries of human cognition through literary imagination.

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